

An innovative lens-based imaging detector for GRAIN in SAND at the DUNE Near Detector Complex

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The Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE) aims to resolve fundamental open questions in neutrino physics, including the neutrino mass ordering and the possible violation of CP symmetry in the lepton sector. Within the DUNE Near Detector complex, the System for on-Axis Neutrino Detection (SAND) will provide continuous on-axis monitoring of the neutrino beam, enabling precise flux determination and a broad program of neutrino interaction measurements. SAND integrates a 0.6 T superconducting solenoid and an electromagnetic calorimeter from the KLOE experiment, together with a tracking system currently under development. Upstream of the tracker, a 1-ton liquid Argon active target, GRAIN (GRanular Argon for Interaction of Neutrinos), will allow detailed reconstruction of ν -Ar interactions. GRAIN will be instrumented with an optical readout system based on a lens and a coded-mask optical detectors.

In this contribution, the current design and status of SAND and GRAIN will be presented, followed by preliminary simulation results of track and vertex reconstruction in GRAIN using the lens configuration.

PRESENTED AT

NuPhys2026, Prospects in Neutrino Physics
King's College, London, UK,
January 7–9, 2026

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1 The DUNE experiment

The Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE) is a next-generation long-baseline neutrino experiment designed to address fundamental questions in neutrino physics [1]. Its primary goals are to determine whether CP symmetry is violated in the lepton sector and, if so, to measure the corresponding CP-violating phase δ_{CP} , to improve precision on the atmospheric mixing angle θ_{23} and determine its octant ($\theta_{23} < \pi/4$ versus $\theta_{23} > \pi/4$), and to establish the neutrino mass ordering with a high confidence level.

DUNE also pursues a broad physics program beyond standard oscillations, including searches for light dark matter, sterile neutrinos, and proton decay. A high-intensity, wide-band neutrino and anti-neutrino beam, initially at 1.2 MW, will be produced at Fermilab in Illinois and directed toward the Far Detector (FD) located at ~ 1300 km away at the Sanford Underground Research Facility (SURF) in South Dakota. The FD will include three large Liquid Argon Time Projection Chambers (LArTPCs) totaling 30 kt fiducial mass, accompanied by an extra module, referred to as the “Module of Opportunity”, which will allow testing and development of alternative detector technologies. The FD modules will be installed ~ 1.5 km underground and will employ both horizontal and vertical drift technologies. A schematic overview of the DUNE experimental setup is shown in Fig.1.

The Near Detector complex will consist of three main components: ND-LAr, the Temporary Muon Spectrometer (TMS) - which in Phase II will be replaced by ND-GAr - and the on-axis detector SAND. A more detailed description of the ND complex is provided in the following section.

Figure 1: The DUNE experiment layout [2].

2 The Near Detector complex

The DUNE Near Detector (ND) complex is designed to provide precise measurements of the unoscillated neutrino beam, which are essential for constraining systematic uncertainties in oscillation analyses [3]. It consists of three complementary subsystems:

ND-LAr, a downstream magnetic spectrometer (TMS), and the on-axis detector SAND - together with the off-axis capability enabled by the DUNE-PRISM program (see Fig.2). The central component, ND-LAr, is a LArTPC based on the ArgonCube technology. By employing the same target nucleus and similar detection principles as the Far Detector, it reduces systematic uncertainties related to nuclear effects and detector response. Its volume is sufficient to ensure hadronic containment and to collect very large interaction samples, enabling precise measurements of neutrino cross sections and beam flux, including through neutrino-electron scattering. However, its acceptance for high-momentum muons is limited, making an additional spectrometer necessary.

This role is fulfilled by TMS, located downstream of ND-LAr. It's designed to detect muons exiting the LAr volume, providing charge identification through its magnetic field and measuring the muon momentum via range and curvature.

A key feature of the ND complex is the DUNE-PRISM program, in which ND-LAr and TMS can move off the beam axis. This allows the experiment to sample neutrino fluxes with different energy spectra: as the detectors move off-axis, the spectrum becomes narrower and shifts to lower energies. This capability enables a data-driven mapping between reconstructed and true neutrino energy, significantly reducing systematic uncertainties associated with near-to-far extrapolation.

Complementing these movable detectors, the System for on-Axis Neutrino Detection (SAND) operates continuously on-axis. It is a magnetized detector equipped with tracking and calorimetric capabilities, allowing it to monitor the stability and composition of the neutrino beam. Within SAND, the GRAIN liquid Argon target provides additional measurements of neutrino interactions on Argon, while the combination of tracker and calorimeter ensures high efficiency in neutron detection and improved characterization of final-state particles.

Together, these subsystems provide a comprehensive and redundant set of measurements of the neutrino flux, interaction cross sections, and detector response, forming the basis for the precise near-to-far extrapolation required by the DUNE oscillation program.

Figure 2: The DUNE Near Detector complex layout [4].

3 The SAND apparatus

SAND is a multipurpose magnetized detector located on the beam axis in the DUNE ND complex [5], [6]. Unlike the movable detectors used in the DUNE-PRISM program, SAND remains permanently on-axis and provides continuous monitoring of the neutrino beam. This capability is essential for tracking beam stability and identifying variations that could affect oscillation analyses. In addition, SAND performs independent measurements of the neutrino and antineutrino flux and flavor composition, providing an important cross-check for the measurements performed by the other Near Detector components during off-axis operation. A side and top view of SAND, together with a view of KLOE magnet, yoke, and barrel ECAL modules are shown in Fig.3. SAND consists of a superconducting solenoidal magnet producing a magnetic field of 0.6 T. The magnet and the surrounding electromagnetic calorimeter (ECAL) are reused from the KLOE experiment. The ECAL is a lead-scintillating fiber sampling calorimeter that provides nearly full angular coverage and enables precise measurements of electromagnetic showers and particle timing.

Inside the magnetic volume, the final design of the tracking system has not yet been established, with two main options currently under consideration: a Straw Tube Tracker (STT) as the baseline solution, and a Drift Chamber as a backup alternative.

Complementing the tracker is an active liquid Argon target, GRAIN, which provides a sample of neutrino interactions on Argon within the SAND detector. The combination of multiple nuclear targets (Ar, C, and CH₂) enables detailed studies of neutrino interaction processes and nuclear effects across different materials. These measurements provide valuable input for interaction modeling.

Together with the other ND components, these measurements play an important role in constraining the neutrino flux, validating interaction models, and supporting the precision oscillation program of DUNE.

Figure 3: *Left*: side and top view of the SAND detector [5]. *Right*: view of the magnet, yoke, and barrel ECAL modules of the KLOE detector, with the inner tracker removed [6].

4 The GRAIN detector

GRAIN (GRanular Argon for Interaction of Neutrinos) is an innovative detector being developed for the upstream region of SAND [5], [6]. Its primary goal is to measure neutrino interactions on Argon while providing complementary information to the other ND subsystems. In particular, GRAIN enables studies of ν -Ar cross sections and nuclear effects. A schematic view of SAND together with the GRAIN detector layout is presented on the left of Fig.4.

The detector consists of an active liquid Argon target contained in a steel vessel placed inside a vacuum cryostat. At the DUNE near site, the very high interaction rate and the presence of pile-up events make the use of traditional LArTPCs challenging because of the long drift times required for charge collection. GRAIN therefore explores a novel detection concept based entirely on the imaging of scintillation light produced in LAr, rather than on charge readout.

LAr is an excellent scintillator, producing $\sim 4 \times 10^4$ γ s/MeV with a fast emission component on the order of a few nanoseconds. However, its scintillation light peaks at a wavelength of 128 nm in the vacuum ultraviolet, where most optical materials are not transparent and detector sensitivity is limited. To address this challenge, the GRAIN concept relies on optical cameras based on arrays of Silicon Photomultipliers (SiPMs) operated at cryogenic temperatures, where their performance benefits from reduced thermal noise. Each camera uses a 32×32 matrix of SiPMs.

Two optical approaches are currently under investigation for the camera system: one based on lens optics and another using coded-aperture masks. Both designs aim to maximize light collection and angular acceptance. A detailed schematic of the GRAIN target showing the detector geometry and main dimensions within the cryostat is shown on the right side of Fig.4.

Figure 4: **Left:** schematic layout of the SAND detector, highlighting the magnetized volume, ECAL, inner tracking system, and the GRAIN LAr cryostat [7]. **Right:** schematic of the GRAIN target showing the detector geometry and main dimensions ($150 \times 150 \times 50$ cm³) within the cryostat [8].

5 An innovative imaging system for GRAIN

GRAIN aims at enhancing the reconstruction of particle interactions [9]. While LAr intrinsically provides both ionization charge and scintillation light signals, charge readout is not a viable option for this detector. The relatively slow drift velocity of electrons in LAr (on the order of $\text{mm}/\mu\text{s}$) would lead to substantial pile-up, given the $\sim 10 \mu\text{s}$ beam spill duration at the ND. Additionally, the geometry of the cryostat makes the implementation of a uniform electric field particularly challenging. For these reasons, the detector will rely exclusively on scintillation light collection.

SiPMs have been chosen as the optimal photodetectors due to their compatibility with cryogenic operation, low noise performance, and compact size, which allows flexible integration within the detector volume. A simple array of SiPMs can provide information on the total deposited energy and timing, but lacks intrinsic spatial resolution.

To achieve spatial resolution, imaging capabilities must be introduced. This is accomplished by segmenting the photodetector into pixels, implemented as 2D arrays of individually read-out SiPMs. Such configurations enable the mapping of light signals to positions in space via optical systems. Two imaging approaches are currently under evaluation.

The first option is based on ultraviolet-sensitive lens systems, similar to those used in conventional cameras. However, their application in LAr requires careful consideration of material properties such as VUV transmittance and refractive indices, as well as optimization of optical parameters.

The second option uses coded aperture imaging, an extension of the pinhole camera concept. In this case, a patterned mask placed in front of the sensor produces a shadow that can be mathematically inverted to reconstruct the original image. This technique is wavelength-independent but demands high photon statistics for accurate reconstruction. The final choice between these technologies will be driven by dedicated cryogenic tests, with the possibility of adopting a hybrid solution to combine their respective advantages.

5.1 The lens imaging system

Optical lenses represent a well-established solution for imaging applications; however, their use in a cryogenic medium such as LAr is non-trivial and requires careful material selection. In particular, the lens material must be compatible with cryogenic conditions, exhibit suitable refractive index matching with LAr, and ensure high transparency at the scintillation wavelength.

At the native LAr scintillation wavelength (127 nm), only a limited set of materials - such as MgF_2 and CaF_2 - are viable for lens production. However, their mechanical and thermal stability in large dimensions and at cryogenic temperatures remains uncertain. To overcome these limitations, a promising strategy consists in doping LAr with small concentrations of Xenon, which shifts the scintillation light from 127 nm to ~ 174 nm.

This wavelength shift improves photon detection efficiency and enables the use of more conventional UV-grade materials, such as fused silica, without degrading the timing performance, since the energy transfer process occurs on the nanosecond scale. The main drawback is a modification of the scintillation time profile, with a shortened slow component.

The design of a lens-based imaging system in LAr is further complicated by the similarity between the refractive indices of LAr and typical optical materials in the UV range. This reduces the focusing power of standard lens geometries. To address this issue, the optical system is based on a gas-filled volume enclosed by refractive surfaces, so that the dominant optical effect arises from the LAr-gas interface.

The proposed design consists of a compact system including a lens assembly, a light shield, and a pixelated SiPM sensor. The optical configuration and the overall camera structure are illustrated in Fig.5. The system is based on two closely spaced plane-convex lenses (diameter 60 mm), optimized through ray-tracing simulations and is designed to satisfy several key requirements: resolving track features at the few mm scale, maximizing the field of view, ensuring sufficient photon collection, and maintaining a distance <10 cm between the lens and the sensor.

Simulation studies show that this configuration achieves an effective focal length of ~ 9 cm and provides adequate light collection for tracks located up to ~ 1.3 m from the lens. The focusing performance depends on the distance of the light source: for distances greater than ~ 40 cm, the image spot size remains below ~ 7 mm, ensuring sufficient spatial resolution to distinguish multiple tracks.

Within this fiducial region, particle tracks are well reconstructed as localized patterns on the SiPM array. Outside this region, images become either highly defocused or uniformly illuminated, providing a natural geometrical selection for well-reconstructed events.

Figure 5: Design of the optical system based on two plane-convex lenses, with an exploded view of the lens-based camera components, including the lenses, the light shield, and the SiPM matrix on a support [9].

6 Tracking performances

Preliminary studies indicate that the lens-based imaging system provides promising spatial reconstruction capabilities. A sample of 20k ν -Ar charged-current interactions with at least 2 charged tracks has been analyzed to evaluate the detector performance. In this configuration, a spatial resolution of ~ 6 mm is achieved for reconstructed interaction vertices, as can be seen in the plots shown in Fig.6, while the resolution on track endpoints is about 30 mm, as can be seen in the plots shown in Fig.7. The latter is particularly relevant for distinguishing contained from exiting particles.

Track and vertex reconstruction in the 3D volume can be performed using two approaches. For completeness, we describe the principles of both methods; however, the results shown in Fig.6 and Fig.7 are obtained using the first approach (image-based method).

1. **Image-based method.** The reconstruction is initially performed in the 2D images acquired by each camera. Tracks are identified using a Hough transform, which efficiently detects linear features in the pixelated SiPM images. Vertices are reconstructed as the intersection points of the identified tracks, while track endpoints are determined from the extremities of the corresponding pixel clusters. The 3D event topology is then obtained by combining and projecting the reconstructed 2D information from multiple views.
2. **Voxel-based method.** The GRAIN volume is discretized into a 3D grid of voxels with a size of 1 cm^3 . Each photon detected by the SiPM array is back-propagated into the detector volume, contributing to the population of compatible voxels. Regions with a high density of back-projected contributions are selected, forming clusters that correspond to particle trajectories. These voxel clusters are subsequently analyzed to extract track parameters and reconstruct interaction vertices.

Figure 6: Residual distribution of the reconstructed vertex position on ν -Ar CC interactions in GRAIN with the lens-based imaging system.

Figure 7: Residual distribution of the reconstructed endpoint position on ν -Ar CC interactions in GRAIN with the lens-based imaging system.

7 Conclusions and Outlook

In conclusion, the Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment will play a central role in addressing some of the most important open questions in neutrino physics through the combined operation of its Near and Far Detector systems.

Within this framework, SAND provides robust and continuous monitoring of the neutrino beam, enabling precise measurements of both the flux normalization and its energy spectrum. These measurements are essential for reducing systematic uncertainties in long-baseline analyses.

The GRAIN detector is designed to further enhance the SAND physics program by providing an additional, complementary sample of neutrino interactions in liquid Argon, thereby improving the overall sensitivity of the experiment.

On the technological side, a prototype of the lens-based optical imaging system is currently under test in Genoa and represents an important step toward validating this novel approach.

Finally, initial simulation studies indicate that the proposed detector concept and reconstruction techniques are highly promising, demonstrating the potential of this technology for precise spatial reconstruction and even characterization in liquid Argon.

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